
VALIDATION OF NUCLEAR GAUGE DENSITY-METER READINGS AGAINST SAND REPLACEMENT METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents wet density and moisture content comparative test results of surface nuclear gauge density-meter against sand replacement method. The test results were obtained by carrying out field density parallel testing, whereby the density and moisture readings were determined first using a nuclear gauge density-meter followed by the sand replacement method. The use of "multiple shift coefficients" developed from a linear regression model as a means of adjusting and calibrating the nuclear gauge density-meter readings against sand replacement test results is proposed.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The nuclear gauge density meter is used in many construction sites to determine the geomaterial field density and moisture content. This method is gaining popularity because it is not laborious; it is quick, and very minimum personnel can be used during the testing operation. The nuclear gauge testing procedure is standardised in BS 1377: Part 9: 1990, AASHTO T238, AASHTO T239, ASTM D2922 and ASTM D3017.

The sand replacement, balloon, and core-cutter are the traditional methods for determining the in-situ density of the compacted embankment and pavement layers. These methods are more accurate than the nuclear gauge method. However, they are laborious, and their repeatability and reproducibility of the test results are poor. All methods require the moisture content to be determined using the oven-dry method, implying that the earth-fill operation will have to be halted for few minutes to allow the density data processing and computation before placing the next embankment layer.

The accuracy of the nuclear gauge in determining wet density and moisture content principally depends on the chemical composition of soil under test and sample heterogeneity. The nuclear gauge is normally calibrated in the factory using material of known density and water content. The calibration is carried out using what is commonly referred to as an "average soil" of known mineralogical/chemical composition. The departure of the mineralogical composition of soil under test from the mineralogical composition of an "average soil" leads to erratic gauge readings. Therefore, on-site calibration of the nuclear gauge density-meter to validate its readings against the sand replacement method is of paramount importance.

The comparison data used in this paper were obtained during the nuclear gauge calibration used for field density testing for the construction of Dar Es Salam [Wazo hill] – Bagamoyo road project in Tanzania.

2.0 TESTING METHODOLOGY

The sections to be tested were divided into subsections depending on the type of material/layer to be tested. The wet density and moisture content was determined first using the Troxler Nuclear gauge density-meter model 3430 in direct transmission mode. Three wet density and moisture readings were taken at each location using a nuclear gauge. The test result for the wet density and the moisture content was taken as the average of three nuclear gauge readings. After that, determination of wet density and moisture content using the sand replacement method followed exactly at the same position where density and moisture content were determined previously using nuclear gauge density-meter.

The testing was divided into three phases, strategically selected to assess the wet

density and moisture content variation for soils with different mineralogical composition used to construct pavement layers. Phase one material was a reddish-brown clayey/silty Sand of low plasticity from Mapinga borrow area used as an improved subgrade layer. Due to its reddish colour, it is presumed that iron oxide is one of the constituents. Phase two material was pit-run coral limestone from Mpiji borrow area used for construction of subbase layer. Calcium carbonate is presumed to be one of the main constituents of this coralline geomaterial. The material tested in phase three was crusher-run material obtained after crushing massive granitic gneiss from Msata Quarry. Its main constituents are quartz, feldspar and a negligible percentage of black mica (biotite).

3.0 TEST RESULTS

3.1 WET DENSITY DATA

The wet density data from nuclear gauge density-meter readings were compared with test results obtained from the sand replacement method using a linear regression model.

The wet density test results of the material tested during phase one [*reddish clayey/Silty sand from Mapinga borrow pit*] indicate that the nuclear gauge density-meter gives a consistently lower value of wet density than the sand replacement method. The best fit linear regression line and line of equality suggest that the accuracy of the test results tends to improve as the value of the wet density increases. The summary of the test results is shown in Figure 1.

The material tested during phase two was coral limestone from Mpiji borrow pit. The summary of the wet density test results is given in Figure 2. The test results indicate that initially, say at around 2200 kg/m³, the nuclear gauge gives a slightly lower value of wet density up to about 2400 kg/m³, beyond this value, the nuclear gauge gives a somewhat higher value of wet density compared to the sand replacement method.

Figure 1: wet density for reddish Mapinga soil ($R^2=0.898$)

Figure 2: Wet density Mpiji Borrow area [$R^2=0.7525$]

The material tested during Phase three was crushed granitic gneiss from Msata quarry. It can be seen from Figure 3 that the nuclear gauge yielded a consistently lower value of wet density compared to the sand replacement method. The results are very comparable, as evidenced by a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.95.

Figure 3: wet density crushed stone base [$R^2=0.95$]

5.2 MOISTURE DATA

The moisture content data for clayey/silty sand soil and coralline gravel sand material are shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. The test results indicate that the nuclear gauge density meter gives higher moisture content than the oven-dry method. It is also observed that for the geomaterial tested, the accuracy of the nuclear gauge in determining the moisture content tends to decrease as the moisture content increases. The trend of nuclear gauge readings to yield higher moisture content is more apparent as the moisture content increases.

Figure 6 shows the correlation of the oven-dry moisture and nuclear gauge moisture readings for crushed stone base. The test results indicate an excellent correlation between the nuclear gauge moisture readings and the oven-dry

Figure 4: Moisture content for clayey/silty sand [Mapinga, $R^2=0.902$]

Figure 5: Moisture Content for coralline material from Mpigi ($R^2=0.89$)

Figure 6: Moisture content crushed stone base ($R^2=0.9533$)

4.0 CORRECTION OF NUCLEAR GAUGE READINGS

The standard and traditional procedure of adjusting the nuclear gauge density meter wet density readings is to find the mean error (single shift coefficient) of the nuclear gauge density metre readings computed using equation 1 as recommended by the nuclear gauge manufacturers.[1]

$$SC = A - B \dots (1)$$

Where,

- SC is the shift coefficient
- A is the average nuclear-wet density
- B is the average balloon, sand replacement or core cutter wet density.

From the test results shown in Figure 1, it can be seen that the nuclear gauge readings are consistently lower than the sand replacement method. However, it is noted that the accuracy of the nuclear gauge readings tends to improve as the wet density increases. The results given in Figure 2 suggest that the nuclear gauge readings of less than 2400 kg/m³ are supposed to be corrected using a negative shift coefficient. In contrast, for the nuclear gauge readings of more than 2400 kg/m³, the nuclear gauge readings require to

be corrected using the positive shift coefficient.

The wet density test results in Figure 3 are for the crushed stone base; the regression line is parallel to the line of equality, suggesting that a single shift coefficient can effectively correct the nuclear gauge readings.

For the moisture content corrections, the operation manual for the Troxler Model 3430 recommends using a single shift coefficient for correcting the moisture content readings against the oven-dry method using the expression shown as equation 2.

$$k = \frac{\%M_{LAB} - \%M_{GAUGE}}{100 + \%M_{GAUGE}} \times 1000 \dots (2)$$

As for the wet density test results, this single moisture content shift coefficient works better when the slope of the regression line is parallel to the line of equality. For the soil tested, the single moisture content shift coefficient works perfectly for the data shown in Figure 6 for the crushed stone base since the slope of the line is very close to 1. For the moisture content test results shown in Figures 4 and 5, the accuracy of the nuclear gauge readings decreases as the moisture content increases, suggesting that the single shift coefficient for correction of the nuclear gauge moisture content readings is not ideal.

4.1 Multiple Shift Coefficient

The perfect correlation between the nuclear gauge readings and the sand replacement method is achieved only when the fitted equation is in the form of

$$y = x \dots (1)$$

Where “y” is the wet density or moisture content as determined using sand replacement or core cutter method, and ‘x’ is wet density or moisture content as determined using a nuclear gauge. Equation (1) suggests that, for a single “shift coefficient” to be used for adjusting the nuclear gauge readings, the slope of the best-

fit line must be equal to a unit (one). In other words, the regression line must be parallel with the line of equality, i.e., “ $y=x$ ”. This implies that to use a single shift coefficient, and the fitted equation should be in the form of

$$y_0 = x + C \dots \dots (3)$$

Where “C” is a constant value which is equivalent to the single shift coefficient.

In practice, it is difficult or impossible to achieve this kind of perfect correlation; as results, the fitted equation is generally in the form of

$$y_1 = mx + C \dots \dots (4)$$

Since the perfect correlation is given by equation (1), the error term (k) for the regression model is

$$k = y - y_1 = x - (mx + C) = (1 - m)x - C \dots \dots (5)$$

This error term (k) represents a “multiple shift coefficients” to be used for adjusting the nuclear gauge density or moisture readings.

4.2 CORRECTION USING MULTIPLE SHIFT COEFFICIENT

Based on equation 5, the correction of the wet density test results shown in Figure 1, 2 and 3 using multiple shift coefficients was carried out. The summary of the test results for the wet density is shown in Figure 7, 8 and 9.

The regression line of the corrected nuclear gauge readings and sand replacement coincides with the line of equality, suggesting that the correction of the nuclear gauge readings using multiple shift coefficients improves the accuracy of the nuclear gauge readings.

Figure 7: corrected wet density for Mapinga ($R^2=0.90$)

Figure 8: corrected wet density for Mpiji soil ($R^2=0.7523$)

Figure 9: Corrected wet density for the crushed stone base ($R^2=$)

The correction of the moisture content data is not presented herein. The same principle of using multiple shift coefficients can be used to correct the nuclear gauge moisture content readings.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The body of tests reported in this study has given some insight into the test results yielded by nuclear gauge compared to the standard method of sand replacement method. The correspondence of the data appears to be reasonable for the material tested during this investigation. Although the accuracy of the gauge in determining both water content and density is largely depending upon the chemical composition of the soil, the nuclear gauge gives reliable results, particularly if its reading is validated against the sand replacement method and corrected using multiple shift coefficients.

REFERENCES

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